

SZ-SB-III-02-02 Search for other Teachers (English)

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Doi	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10091531
ID	SZ-Sb-02-02
Title	Search for other Teachers
Educational area	#school #adult-education
Persona	P: Selin - Teacher https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10091270
Short description	Selin Sonntag is looking for other teachers (group) to exchange ideas about everyday working life/further training/resilience.
Result	Networking, exchange and collaborative work on an OER.
Process	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Problem scenario• Activity scenario• Process "Contact with other teachers"
Preconditions	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Selin is registered at BIRD• Selin is logged in to BIRD• Selin has created a Buddyfinder profile
Components	#buddyfinder #workspace #chat
Services / tools	

Problem scenario

Introduction

Selin Sonntag gets along well with her colleagues, but many of the teachers at her comprehensive school are very busy and not open to changes and suggestions for improvement. Yet, in Selin's eyes, there is so much that can be improved and simplified. She has many ideas, but she lacks someone with whom she can talk about how to implement these ideas. Fundamentally, she wishes for more support and openness from her teaching staff.

Problem definition

Selin wants to exchange ideas with other teachers who are in a similar situation and trying to make a difference. She wants to learn more about the ideas and actions of

other teachers so that she can initiate changes herself.

Background and context

Reforms and changes in schools are difficult, but Selin believes that individual commitment is important. She is alone with her ideas at her school and therefore finds groups particularly important, as they can offer the support and exchange that is not available in her immediate environment. She would like to have a group of like-minded people with whom she could have a kind of regular meeting and discuss things on an ongoing basis.

Impact of the problem (on the Persona)

Selin feels reasonably confident using various media and technologies in class, including the smartboard. She enjoys trying out new ideas, resources, and apps and is convinced that teaching and learning is more than just imparting subject knowledge. The majority of her teaching staff are reluctant to try new pedagogical approaches or tools and are dismissive when she expresses new ideas. Her motivation is slowly waning, and she feels isolated. She doesn't want to stop thinking about possible changes so that she can possibly initiate something herself. To put these ideas into practice, she would like people to give her feedback.

Pre BIRD attempts at a solution

Selin has already "browsed" a few online forums for teachers, but hasn't yet found a group dedicated to new, innovative ideas and school reforms. The topic has been mentioned in some comments, but Selin would have to log into these forums and reply to them, hoping that the commenters would respond again. Selin finds that a bit too tedious, and there's no guarantee that anyone will actually respond. She would prefer to find a group that deals exclusively with this topic.

Activity scenario

Process "Contact with other teachers"

Step 1: Selin opens BIRD and navigate to the Buddyfinder

Step 2: In the Buddy Finder, she enters the following in the search query:

- State: Open
- City: Open, except Cologne
- School: Integrated Comprehensive School (IGS)
- Target group: Exchange/ancestral/working life/continuing education/resilience
- subject: Open

- Group or Individual: Group

Step 3: The Buddy Finder suggests to Selin a group of teachers who have already formed a group and are looking for additional members.

Step 4: On the (geographical) map, Selin sees that the group is made up of teachers from different federal states and already includes 10 people.

Step 5: She finds the composition of the group valuable because she seeks exchange with teachers from different federal states and is also interested in the different experiences and school types from state to state.

Step 6: Selin sends the group a contact request via the Buddyfinder and briefly explains her request in the message field.

Step 7: She will be added to the group and given access to the group's shared workspace.

Step 8: First, Selin opens the group chat to briefly introduce herself to the other teachers and thank them for joining the group.

Strong 9: She then navigates to the workspace and can click through the various folders in which, among other things, previously collected tips and discussions have been documented.